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Hydrogeology Of Obinofia Ndiuno And Environs

Aniebone, V.O. PhD., Dankadai, A.B., Garba, I. & Yusuf, A.K.

Nigeria Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research, Victoria Island, Lagos
Corresponding author: Aniebone Victor Obiora. Email: aniebonevic@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The hydrogeologic features of Obinofia Ndiuno and its environs were mapped out in this study. The area has a quite good number of surface and ground water resources. There are a lot of boreholes at different locations within the study area. In the course of this survey, water sample from Obinofia Ndiuno famous spring was collected and analysed chemically and the results interpreted. The results of the analysis proved the water potable and satisfied the World Health Organisation standard for drinking water. The colour, hydrogen ion concentration, PH, total hardness, total iron, chloride, nitrates, among others were tested. The surface water resources of the area such as the rivers, streams and lakes were mapped out and studied. The famous Heneke Lake was studied and the potentials identified. Major rivers like Ajali and Oji were given a look at hydrogeologically. The pollution sources in the area were identified.

Keywords: Hydrogeology, Obinofia Ndiuno, Southeast Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Obinofia Ndiuno and its environs located in the Anambra Basin Southeastern Nigeria is blessed with striking geologic features (Fig.1). The geology of Obinofia Ndiuno and its environs has for years drawn the attentions of geologists, students of geology, generalists (geographers) and the government. This is due to the presence of important geologic features such as the Ogba cave, the warm spring and the Heneke Lake which is comparable in size to the famous Agulu Lake in Anambra state. The area has a lot of surface water bodies including rivers, springs and lakes. Some of the rivers are Ajali, Oji and Dodo rivers. We also have the Heneke and Orinkita lakes and numerous warm and cold springs including the Ogba stream where the famous Ogba cave is located. In the area, a number of subsurface water sources (boreholes) were identified which include artesian wells. The source being the aquiferous Ajali Sandstone and the fractured Nsukka Sandstone unit. There is scarcity of published works in the geology/hydrogeology of Obinofia Ndiuno and its environs despite the many geologic features in the place. Hence this study is necessary so as to highlight them. The objective of this study is to map out and identify the water resources potentials of the study area.

STUDY AREA

The study area is located within latitudes $6^{\circ} 15'N$ to $6^{\circ} 21'N$ and longitudes $7^{\circ} 12'E$ to $7^{\circ} 18'E$. It is about 121 square kilometers and is within the Anambra basin. The basin is located at the southwestern end of the Benue Trough and bounded on the eastern and southwestern flanks by the Abakaliki Anticlinorium and the Benin Hinge line respectively. It stretches for about 300 kilometers in a northeast – southwest direction and has width of 160 km at the southeast tip and 48km in the northeast extremes (Whiteman, 1982). The dominant topographic features of the area are the ridges that form parts of the Nsukka-Udi-Okigwe Cuesta (Figure 1). The terrain rises from as low as 61.0 meters in Mgbagbu-Owa to 457.0 meters in Abia town as a dome shaped hill with many outliers, highly indented ridges and gullies (Nwozor,

2002). The mapped area covers part of the western dip slopes of Udi escarpment and eastern section of the Mamu/Anambra plains. The area has a local relief of 350.6m. Physiographically, the area is characterized by a gentle, undulating landscape which generally slopes towards the south-west. The bedrock of the area comprises the sedimentary rocks of upper cretaceous (Reyment 1965). The plain which is the dominant feature in the area is composed of sedimentary rocks which are largely sandstones, shales and clays of cretaceous and tertiary ages (Ofomata, 1975). There are two main relief areas; the Umana Ndiuno which attain a height of about 600 to below 900meters above sea level with flat top and is trending in the direction NW-SE direction. The second ridge is trending in the direction NE-SW runs from Aguobu Umumba through Omughu Umana and terminated at Ihuezi Obinofia Ndiuno and attain a height of 100 to 200 meters above sea level (fig 1). The study area records a mean annual temperature of 31.2°C. According to Monanu (1975).

The climate of the area is 'AM' following Koppens classification which implies an average rainfall surplus. It has a maximum of 34.3°C and a minimum of 28.3°C. The area records annual rainfall of 1,939mm. It has a maximum of 462.6mm and a minimum of 0.0mm. The vegetation belongs to the rain

Figure 1. Topographic Map of the Study Area

forest savanna, a greater percentage of the vegetation cover being under grass. The vegetation is being controlled by drainage and the topography. The moderately high ridge area support grassy vegetation with drought resistant deep rooted shrubs that are randomly distributed, whereas in the central low lying area shally areas, in the river valleys and banks the bush vegetation dominates (Igbozurike, 1975).

GEOLOGY OF THE STUDY AREA

The study area is underlain by three stratigraphic units. These formations are Ajali Sandstone of Upper Maastrichtian stage, Nsukka Formation of Upper Maastrichtian to Lower Paleocene and the third the Imo Shale. The Imo Shale Formation was deposited during the Paleocene time to Lower Eocene time. Ajali Sandstone is conformably overlain by the Nsukka Formation (Fig. 2)

Figure 2. Geologic Map of the Study Area

THE DESCRIPTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE GEOLOGIC FORMATIONS OF THE STUDY AREA

Ajali Sandstone

The Ajali Sandstone is one of the three stratigraphic units underlying the study area and it covers more than 70% of the study area (Fig. 2). Ajali Sandstone consists of thick, friable, poorly sorted sandstone typically white in colour but sometimes iron-stained (Bain, 1924).

A marked banding of coarse and fine layers is displayed. The sand grains and large fragments are sub angular, with a sparse cement of white clay. This formation is of large scale cross-stratification with grains ranging from coarse through medium to fine sizes and the beddings are massive at the base and become thinly laminated upward. The formation is underlain by a considerable thickness of red earth, which consists of red, earthy sands, formed by the weathering and ferruginisation of the formation. The formation is well displayed in the study area as found in outcrop of rock exposure within Ogba stream in Ihuezi village Obinofia Ndiuno and along Ajali river bank. On the Udi Plateau, the red earth may be as much as thirty meters thick. North of the Oji River, the higher slopes of the Enugu escarpment consist of the Ajali Formation. Good exposures of the sandstones occurs in the deep gullies incised along the higher slopes of the scarp. The Ajali Sandstone is conformably overlain by the Nsukka Formation (Upper Coal Measures), while the Imo Shale Formation which was deposited during the Paleocene time to lower Eocene time overlies the Nsukka Formation (Fig.2).

Nsukka Formation

The formation was earlier described as Upper Coal Measures by Tattam (1944), Dupreez (1947), Simpson (1948) but was later named Nsukka Formation by Reyment (1965). The Formation is of Upper Maastrichtian to Lower Paleocene age. The Nsukka Formation lies conformably on the Ajali Sandstone and occupies a broad stretch of country west of Udi Plateau It occupies 15% of the mapped area. In the study area, the formation outcrops in various places in the study area These areas are around Ihuezi village Obinofia Ndiuno, Ojinato Ugwuoba Nachi e.t.c In these locations the formation shows the following sequence of deposits starting from bottom with sandstone, shale and siltstone units and occasionally clay intercalations and lateritic capping..The formation has a regional dips varying between 100 to 150SW and striking NW-SE. The rocks consist of an alternating succession of sandstone, dark shale and sandy shale, with thin coal seam at various horizons. The Nsukka Formation in the mapped area consists of two units; the sandstone unit and shale unit. The formation consists also of carbonaceous shales which may contain bands and lens of impure coal. The formation gives rise to the numerous springs along the slopes of the outliers.

Imo Shale

The Imo Shale Formation was deposited during the Paleocene time to lower Eocene time (Stauble et al, 1967, Weber et al, (1975). The Imo Shale occupies 15% of the mapped area. Imo Shale comprises predominantly argillaceous rocks underlying most parts of the eastern lowlands. The Shales contain occasional intercalations of thin bands of calcareous sandstone, marls and limestone (Reyment, (1965).On the basis of lithology and convenience of description, the Imo Shale encountered in the study [area comprises a series of yellowish brown shale with intercalation of sandstone. In some places the shales are bluish to dark in colour as observed in Akpata stream within the study area. Mudcracks are sedimentary features associated with shales and mudstones that are exposed to surface conditions and these features are observed in the formation. The shales are capable of absorbing and retaining water after rain and swell, under the heat of the sun, with much of the water being evaporated resulting to the shrinkage and subsequent mudcrackings.

METHODOLOGY

A reconnaissance survey was first carried out to observe the general physiographic features in the area in order select localities of interest. After this, detailed field work was carried out which involved the study of the lithology sequences and units, the dip and strike measurements. Borehole and well records, surface

water data, geological and hydro-geological reports plus topographic and geologic maps were all obtained from relevant establishments, including school libraries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Water Resources

The existence and distribution of water, both surface and ground water are controlled by structural, textural and meteorological factors. This area experiences heavy precipitation during the wet season which recharges the rivers and increase the water level. These rivers during this season (rainy season) carry sediments which later are deposited on the continental shelf. The water resources of Obinofia Ndiuno and its environs can be subdivided into two groups:

- (1) Surface resources (Rivers, Streams, Lakes)
- (2) Groundwater resources (Boreholes and Springs)

Surface Water Resources (Rivers and Lakes)

The study area is drained by major rivers like Ajali River, Oji River and Dodo River. Others are Akpata, Ukwumboyi, Ekpe, Ngene Akwu in Ugwuoba, Okputo streams which are seasonal including numerous springs and the Ogba stream. Most of these become dry or low in their water level during the dry season. Owing to the effects of silting up stream there was a capture at the Oji River main channel along Okposhi village, Obinofia Ndiagu diverting the whole flow to its tributary Figure 3. Apart from rivers and streams in the area, the area has two lakes namely: Heneke and Orinkita. These lakes including the Ogba cave and the warm and cold springs are being considered suitable for tourist complexes.

Figure 3. OJI RIVER MAIN CHANNEL NOW BUSHY DUE CAPTURE AND SILTING UP STREAM AT OKPOSHI

- **Heneke Lake In Omughu Umana**

Heneke Lake lies within Omughu Umana town except at a point it meandered a little into a boundary area between Omughu and Obinofia Ndiuno. The Heneke Lake is quite comparable in size to the famous Agulu Lake in Anambra state. It is about five square kilometers and about 6.9 meters deep (Okafor, 2015, figure 4). The lake has its source at a place called Onu-Heneke passing through the entire length of Omughu town and eventually narrowing into a stream size at Omughu Bridge where it joins the Ajali River. The community from this area gets their water supply from Ajali River and Heneke Lake. The Heneke Lake has a natural habitat for fish breeding and fishing activities are being carried out by the local fishermen. The lake also attract quite a lot of visitors from within and across the state, just to watch the gracefulness of this lake and the many crocodiles that inhabit there. These animals would certainly provide an interesting game reserve, if harnessed by the government would yield substantial revenue. The

lake is large enough to accommodate any kind of boat-ride and yatching activities. The land surrounding the lake is level and devoid of serious escarpment and so the possibility of constructing a beach there would be with a minimum cost. There is expanse of land for a meaningful development in terms of hotel and other structures which would make the Heneke Lake center an aesthetic.

Figure 4. An Overview of the Heneke Lake

GROUND WATER RESOURCES (Boreholes and Springs)

The aquiferous Ajali Sandstone provide good source of water supply in the mapped area. This is because of highly porous and permeable nature of the sandstone which could favor easy permeation of water down to the saturation zone. Because the Ajali Sandstone is medium to coarse grained it becomes a high yielding aquifer hence the fine grain clayey sand and shaly sand form separating aquitards. The Nsukka sandy shale are poorly aquiferous and may act as an aquitard while the fractured Nsukka Sandstone are also aquiferous.

The study area is blessed with numerous springs and virtually all the communities have one or two motorized boreholes and majority of the boreholes are artesian wells. The artesian wells are of great depths. The approximate depth of boreholes in the study areas is about 200 meters. The deepest among them is the Umumba Ndiagu borehole with a depth of about 494 meters. From the boreholes data one can delineate depths to water table in those areas. Moreover, the data gave confirmation to the formations encountered during the mapping. The data also gave information on the near approximate depths to which wells can be drilled within the mapped area. Also the borehole data gotten from Umumba Ndiagu confirmed the existence of Imo Shale and showed that water in this area can be gotten at a very great depth at about 416 to 494 meters. The well is artesian.

The study area has numerous springs which serve as water sources beside the surface water sources before the advent of boreholes.

Based on the topography of the study area, it was inferred that the elevated areas form the recharge source and the lowlands equally form the discharge zones. This elevated area is attributed to the Ajali Sandstone which has high water potential. The medium to coarse grained sandy units gave rise to aquifers, while the fine clayey sand and shaly siltstone form the separating aquitards. The aquifer parameter for Ajali Sandstone and the computed hydraulic conductivity (K) for Ajali and Nsukka Sandstone are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE.1 AQUIFER PARAMTERS FOR AJALI SANDSTONE (Egboka B.C.E., 1983)

Hydraulic conductivity	$5.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{cms}^{-1}$
Groundwater discharge	$11.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{mhr}^{-1}$
Specific discharge	$2.94 \text{m}^3 \text{mm}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$
Total discharge	224.31m^3
Transmissivity	$46.10 \text{m}^2 \text{hr}^{-1}$

TABLE.2. COMPUTED HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY (K) FOR AJALI SANDSTONE AND NSUKKA FORMATION (ANIEBONE, 1999)

METHODS	AJALI SANDSTONE	NSUKKA
FORMATION		
HARTEMAN ET AL	$2.83 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$	$2.26 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$
HAZEN METHOD	$4.42 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$	$3.54 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$
BEAR METHOD	$2.67 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$	$2.14 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$

From the table above one sees the hydraulic conductivities (K) for Ajali Sandstone and Nsukka Formation computed using three different methods. The value $4.42 \times 10^{-2} \text{cm/s}$ using Hazen method for Ajali Sandstone can be said to tally with that of Egboka B.C.E. 1893 above

Geological Analysis Of Warm And Cold Spring At Obinofia Ndiuno

A spring is a concentrated discharge of ground water appearing at the ground surface as a current of water flow. A spring may flow either continuously or intermittently and its water may be cold or warm, hard or soft. Almost no water is free from dissolved or suspended materials, but the nature and quantity varies widely from region to region. Ground water ordinarily has been filtered through the earth before it again comes to the surface. It is therefore relatively free from mud, and other suspended materials. On the other hand, ground water contains dissolved minerals and some of these, such as sulphur or iron may impart to the water a disagreeable taste. Some minerals give tonic, laxative or other medicinal qualities to the water. Springs are classified in a number of ways and this can be on magnitude of discharge, chemical characteristics, water temperature, geologic structure etc. Warm spring also known as thermal spring contains healthful minerals such as sodium chloride, sodium bicarbonate, potassium etc. These mineral waters are said to give relief to people suffering arthritis, infantile paralysis, rheumatism, high blood pressure. A water sample was collected from the Obinofia Ndiuno spring and analyzed. The spring water is of high quality and only requires treatment before bottling.

Physico-Chemical Status Of Obinofia Ndiuno Spring Water

Hydro geochemistry relates to chemical composition of water to its various uses. In doing this, surface and ground water should be analyzed with respect to chemical nature of rocks in contact with the water. In the course of this survey, water sample from Obinofia Ndiuno spring was collected and analyzed chemically at the Enugu state water Board. The colour, hydrogen ion concentration, PH, total hardness, nitrates etc. were tested for. The results are discussed below as applicable

Colour: - The stipulated maximum desirable colour of drinking water stands at 5 Hazen units, hence the water sample from the study area has exactly 5 Hazen, hence fit for use.

PH: - The hydrogen ion-concentration of the sampled water stand at 6.8mg/L as against the World Health Organisation standard of the range 7.0 – 8.5. For this range of PH, water can serve as drinking water, for irrigation and other industrial purposes, hence the water is portable.

Total Hardness: - (Total Magnesium and Calcium hardness). The total analyses of the water sample collected from the study area shows a value of 4mg/L as against the maximum desirable hardness for drinking water which stood at 100mg/L. This shows that the water has an acceptable hardness, and could then be termed soft water and good for human use.

Nitrates:-Nitrates are produced during the oxidation of nitrogenous organic matters from sewage manures or the leaching fertilizers. In the sampled water the concentration stand at nil as against 0.1mg/L by (WHO). This shows that the spring water is free from nitrates and hence portable.

Total Iron:- (Fe) The undesirable effect of iron in water when in excess is highly noticeable in the water taste, discoloration deposits, the growth of iron bacteria and turbidity. The iron content of the sampled water stood at 0.25mg/L as against WHO maximum iron concentration permissible of 1.0mg/L. From this, the iron content fall within the standard, and hence portable.

Chloride:- Above the limit of 600ppm, as specified by WHO, chloride in water affects the water taste and causes corrosion in hot water system. The chloride content of the water stands at 1.2mg/L for chlorides as Cl. The chloride level from the sampled water is quite low and hence the water is portable.

Pollution

The major pollutants that gave rise to land and water pollution in the area are:

- (1) Human and Animal faeces. Most of the people do not have toilets in their houses and hence bush method is employed.
- (2) Indiscriminate dumping of household and grinding mill wastes/refuse.
- (3) Palm Oils and bread fruit productions, including domestic wastes and effluents are discharged directly into the streams and rivers.
- (4) Agro Chemicals – such as pesticides, gammalin 20 and fertilizers got leached out of the soil into rivers and streams. This is most common in Ajali Sandstone and Nsukka sandstone unit due to their porosity and permeability. Also leaching of sulphur ions and chloride as well as dissolved solids into the rivers and streams has adverse effects on aquatic animals as well as human beings.

CONCLUSION

The study area is underlain by three geologic formations which includes; the Ajali Sandstone, the Nsukka Formation and the Imo Shale. The Ajali Sandstone and Nsukka Sandstone unit constitute the sources of ground water in the area. Virtually every community has one or more motorized boreholes serving the water needs of the populace. There are lots of spring water in the area but only the one at Obinofia Ndiuno was collected and analyzed and was found to be of good quality for domestic use. The major surface water bodies in the area are the Ajali River and Oji River. Others are smaller streams like Akpata, Ekpe, Inyi agu, Okpuata, Dodo, and Ogba streams etc. Most of the streams are perennial. Owing to the effects of silting up stream there was a capture at the Oji River main channel along Okposhi village, Obinofia Ndiagu diverting the whole flow to its tributary (plate1). The major lake in the area, the Heneke Lake is of considerable large size of about two and half kilometers in length and breadth of about 60 meters (plate 2). The lake can be put to a lot of uses if its potentials are being harnessed. Of such uses are fish breeding, game reserve, boat-ride and yatching. Apart from Heneke Lake, there is another less important one, the Orinkita Lake. Topographically, the area is undulating and consists of ridges, valleys, spurs, lowlands and isolated hills. Based on the topography of the study area, it was inferred that the elevated areas form the recharge source and the lowlands equally form the discharge zones. The major sources of pollution in the area are that of human and animals (mostly cattle dung) of the Fulani headmen parading the whole place. We also have household wastes and agro-chemicals. All these in one way or the other find their way into surface water sources.

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